

OPTIMIZATION OF SYMMETRICALLY LAMINATED COMPOSITES RECTANGULAR PLATES

Antonio Miravete*
(Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Zaragoza, SPAIN)

ABSTRACT

Optima laminate configurations for laminated rectangular plates under uniform transverse load are investigated. Laminate thickness and fiber orientation are treated as design variables, the thickness laminate being variable along the plate. A fully stressed iterative procedure and a quadratic failure criteria have been applied in order to get the lightest plate keeping mechanical characteristics. A finite element method accounting for in-plane and interlaminar strains has been used. Results for thin and thick plates and different boundary conditions are shown.

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials have been increasingly used during the last decades, in order to light structures in fields like aeronautics and space. Two steps are essential in the process of taking advantage of this kind of materials: design and optimization.

Optimization of composite structures is a recent issue. This is due to the fact that both optimization techniques and composite structures have been developed during the last few decades and therefore, the conjunction of both of them is even more recent.

Since many kinds of ground and air vehicles have rectangular plates as a common structural element, an increasing demand for improved structural efficiency in such applications has resulted. There are a number of advantages of such materials other than their high stiffness to density values: for example, their capability of being tailored by adequate orientation of the filaments in the various layers in order to optimize the desired structural behavior. Actually, although there is a lot of literature related to plate analysis, the most modern references lack adequate information which could allow a designer to tailor or synthesize an optimal design.

The first attempt in composite optimization seems to be due to Morz [1], who tried to obtain the optimal reinforcement using strength as a design criteria. Bryzgalin[2] and Love and Melchers[3] used a stiffness criteria to get an optimal design of constant thickness composites.

* Presently, Visiting Scientist at the Air Force Materials Laboratory, AFWAL/MLBM, Wright-Patterson AFB, Ohio 45433

Lai and Abenbach[4] used a direct search procedure to obtain an optimal design for minimum tensile stress at the interface in a layered structure subjected to time harmonic and transient loads. Khot[5] suggested an efficient optimization technique based on strain energy distribution and a numerical search for the minimum weight design of structures. The procedure takes into account multiple loading conditions and displacement constraints on the structure. Schmit and Farshi[6] presented a method for minimum weight design of symmetric composite laminates subjected to multiple in-plane loading conditions. Hayashi [7] optimized the fiber volume fractions for columns and orientation angle for plates and cylinders for corresponding buckling strength.

Chao and others[8] determined the optimum fiber orientation for a symmetric orthotropic composite laminate with inplane loading. Hirano[9] optimized the buckling load of laminated plates under uniaxial and biaxial compression. The fiber orientation of each ply is treated as a design variable. Bert[10] presented a technique for obtaining the optimal laminate design for a thin plate consisting of multiple layers of equal thickness composite laminae, the design criteria being maximization of fundamental frequency.

Joshi and Iyengar[11] studied the minimum weight design of composite plates subjected to in-plane and transverse loads treating fiber orientation and thickness of plies as design variables. Soni and Iyengar[12] reported their studies on optimum design of clamped laminated plates. In a recent design paper Joshi and Iyengar[13] reported their studies on optimum design under inplane loads with multiple design variables. More recent works can be found in [14-19].

None of the papers mentioned above considered interlaminar stresses. Bending problems were analysed by means of the Reissner-Stavsky theory[20] and therefore, only thin plates could be studied.

In this work, an attempt is made to optimize rectangular composite plates. Laminate thickness and fiber orientation are treated as design variables.

FORMULATION AND ANALYSIS

The problem here analysed can be formulated by means of the following points:

- A. The objective is to get the optimum structure (the lightest) keeping mechanical characteristics. The criteria here applied is the fully stressed iterative procedure. Further information can be found in [21].
- B. Only symmetric and balanced laminates have been considered.
- C. Boundary conditions are restricted to simply supported and clamped along the four edges of the plate.
- D. Owing to practical considerations, only four angles have been used : 0,+45,-45 and 90 degrees.

A schematic description of the approach suggested is given in Figure 1.

Fig. 1 Representation of the optimization procedure.

The results given by the finite element method are optimized by means of the fully stressed iterative procedure. Laminate thickness and fiber orientation are modified in each step in order to get the lightest plate. Once the design variables have been optimized, a quadratic failure criteria is applied in each element. If the stresses in all the elements satisfy τ is criteria, the process is over. If not, another iteration starts. Usually, around ten iterations are needed to get convergence.

The finite element used here is based on the higher order shear theory [22] and on the penalty function theory. This scheme makes possible to analyse thin and thick plates due to its general formulation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The formulation described above has been applied to the following cases:

- A. $a=0.2$ m for thin plates and $a=0.01$ m for thick plates.
- B. Uniform load $Q=1.E6$ N/m*m for thin plates and $Q=2.E8$ N/m*m for thick plates.

Initial studies showed that the plate aspect ratio has a strong influence on the results. Hence different plate aspect ratios have been implemented (from $a/b=1$ to $a/b=10$). Plate aspect ratios higher than 10 are not interesting because the plate behaviour becomes unidimensional.

The material used is T300/N5208.

THIN, SIMPLY SUPPORTED PLATES AND UNIFORM LOAD

Fig.2 Optimum plate for $a/b=1$.

Fig.3 Optimum plate for $a/b=2$.

- a) a/b : 1 to 1.75 . Optimum laminate: $[45/-45]_n s$. Weight Saving : 27 to 21% .
- b) a/b : 1.75 to 2.25 . Optimum laminate: $[0/45/-45]_n s$. Weight Saving : 21 to 15% .
- c) a/b : 2.25 to 3.5 . Optimum laminate: $[0(5)/45/-45]_n s$. Weight Saving : 15 to 18% .
- d) a/b : 3.5 to 10 . Optimum laminate: $[0]_n$. Weight Saving : 15 to 25% .

THICK, SIMPLY SUPPORTED PLATES AND UNIFORM LOAD

Fig.4 Optimum plate for $a/b=1$.

Fig.5 Optimum plate for $a/b=2$.

- a) a/b : 1 to 3.5 . Optimum laminate: $[45/-45]_n s$. Weight Saving : 18 to 36% .
- b) a/b : 3.5 to 10 . Optimum laminate: $[0]_n$. Weight Saving : 36 to 44% .

THIN, CLAMPED PLATES AND UNIFORM LOAD

Fig.6 Optimum plate for $a/b=1$.

Fig.7 Optimum plate for $a/b=2$.

- a) a/b : 1 to 1.5 . Optimum laminate: $[0/90]_n s$. Weight Saving : 30 to 44% .
- b) a/b : 1.5 to 4.4 . Optimum laminate: $[0(5)/90(2)]_n s$. Weight Saving : 48 to 25% .
- c) a/b : 4.4 to 10 . Optimum laminate: $[0]_n$.Weight Saving : 25 to 38% .

THICK, CLAMPED PLATES AND UNIFORM LOAD

Fig.8 Optimum plate for $a/b=1$.

Fig.9 Optimum plate for $a/b=2$.

- a) a/b : 1 to 3 . Optimum laminate: $[45/-45]_n s$. Weight Saving : 45 to 47% .
- b) a/b : 3 to 10 . Optimum laminate: $[0]_n$. Weight Saving : 47 to 49% .

Results described above make a point of the fact that composite plates can be worthily optimized by tailoring properly the material and by orienting adequately the fiber. The final configuration is function of the boundary conditions and the ratio thickness/length.

A parameter to be considered is the plate aspect ratio. On the one hand, a square plate is a bidimensional structure and such a case usually presents complex configurations with stress concentrations on the corners or central parts of the edges. In this case, the optimum laminate is $[45/-45]_n$ or $[0/90]_n$. On the other hand, a plate whose aspect ratio is 10, behaves like a beam and final distributions are unidimensional. As expected, the optimum laminate is $[0]_n$.

Thick laminates present better weight saving than thin ones owing to the fact that shear distributions have larger margin of variation than bending ones.

Finally, clamped plates are worthier to optimize than simply supported ones, due to the differences in bending and shear distributions.

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